

Method Submission Template for the CSS Toolkit

- 1. Method title (75 characters max):** Impact House for Co-Evaluation
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- 3. Organization:** ZSI - Center for Social Innovation, The Innovation Growth Lab
- 4. Related step from the research cycle:** (Co-)Evaluation
- 5. Related topic from the research cycle:** Ethics, co-evaluation
- 6. Keywords (3-5):** Co-Evaluation, Impact assessment, Stakeholder mapping, Co-design
- 7. Time needed:** 1-3 hours
- 8. Group size:** 5-10 people
- 9. Materials:**

Basic [Printer, flipchart, markers, papers, sticky notes/cardboard cards, room, tables]
and/or technical [Computers/smartphones, digital whiteboard, communication software]

10. Short description of the method (750 characters max):

The impact house is a tool that supports a group to define common foci for co-evaluation and collective impact assessment. The method can be employed at a large scope to help structure the entire evaluation process at the beginning of a project in a participatory way. It can also be employed at a smaller scale to choose specific activities and outcomes to evaluate in a participatory way. This is especially helpful if there is limited time and resources available within a project.

11. Aim: What is the aim of this method?

The impact house can be employed at different levels:
It can be used as a tool to decide on project outcomes and longer-term impacts, and how these would be measured at any point in the implementation of the project.
It can also be used as a tool in the evaluation of the project process and thus support the smooth implementation of a project with many different stakeholder interests.
In any case, the impact house helps to define a common impact vision as a group, and decide how to measure and make measurable the effects of project activities.

12. Who to involve: Who does this method involve?

This method works best if the main stakeholders of the project are involved, including co-researchers. Through this, it can become a tool to structure a true co-evaluation.

13. Further materials: Are there any further materials? Briefly describe the use of the above listed materials and/or include any additional, specific information that users may need.

This method can either be implemented online or in a physical setting.

In online spaces, a shared digital whiteboard is needed where an impact house template is prepared for participants to work on together. Additionally, communication software for online calls is essential. [Computers/smartphones, digital whiteboard, communication software]

For physical meetings, the impact house needs to be printed or drawn on a flipchart. Ideally, the templates will be filled with sticky notes, so notes can still be moved around in the house during discussion. It is also possible to write directly into the open spaces themselves. [Printer, flipchart, markers, papers, sticky notes/cardboard cards, room, tables]

14. Step-by-step: What are the individual steps of this method? (list the actions to apply this method).

The impact house is filled from the bottom to the top, although this structure is not exceedingly strict.

1. Starting at the bottom, first ask: “What does success look like at the end of the project for the various stakeholder groups involved?” Think about the concrete interests and expectations each stakeholder group has that are relevant to the project and use sticky notes to add them in each respective field.
2. Then, think about concrete activities and outputs implemented in the project. What concrete steps will you undertake to achieve the success of the project and for the various stakeholders? What stakeholder groups will actually be involved? What are the goals and non-goals of these activities?
3. From these, look for opportunities of evaluating these project activities together with your stakeholders. Which activities and outputs lend themselves well to co-evaluation, and how? If you have limited resources available, you might want to consider which activities and outputs are the most relevant to the project, and focus on these for co-evaluation.
4. Frame all of this with the roof of the common goals and expected impacts beyond the project runtime.
5. Finally, choose a focus for the co-evaluation, and define which method (approach) would fit best to evaluate this together with your participants (e.g., impact drawings, network maps, cultural probes, story telling, etc.). Always try to fit the method to the interests and capabilities of the involved stakeholder group, and don’t be afraid to get creative!
6. The impact house can also be adapted to other needs and may include fields for potential challenges and risks, champions and blockers. Remember that potential blockers can be turned into champions by involving them in a CSS process early on!

**15. (Optional) Open field: does this method require a specific section?
If so, give us a section title (max 3 words) and related description on the method.**

No specific section necessary

16. Documents: Are there any downloads that this method is linked to?

No downloads

17. Gallery: Please add related images (max 5).

Impact Vision

Impact Vision

